

Impact of Digital Content Marketing on Consumer Purchase Decision in the Egyptian Luxury Car Market

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Abstract:

This study investigates the impact of Digital Content Marketing (DCM) and Social Media Influencer (SMI) characteristics on consumers' purchase decision in the Egyptian luxury car market. The research aims to examine how different dimensions of DCM and SMI influence purchase decision outcomes, including online search evaluation and intention–decision to purchase. The study adopts a quantitative research approach using a structured questionnaire distributed to owners and potential consumers of premium and exotic cars in Egypt through a non-probability judgmental quota sampling technique. A total of 100 valid responses were analyzed using SPSS.

Correlation and regression analysis were employed to test the proposed hypotheses and examine the relationships among the variables. The findings reveal that DCM is the dominant predictor of purchase decision outcomes. Specifically, experiential value, social value, and functional value significantly influence consumers' purchase decisions, while informative and unique values demonstrate limited direct effects when examined independently. However, the combined informative–experiential–social value construct emerged as a strong and consistent predictor of purchase decision outcomes.

The findings also indicate that SMI characteristics have a more limited effect compared to DCM. Authenticity was identified as the only significant and consistent SMI dimension influencing purchase intention and purchase decision, whereas homophily, parasocial relationship, persuasion knowledge, and purchase intention showed no significant direct effects in the regression models.

The study contributes to digital marketing and influencer marketing literature within the luxury automotive sector in Egypt and highlights the importance of authentic, engaging, and value-driven digital content in influencing consumer behavior.

Keywords: Digital Content Marketing, Social Media Influencer, Purchase Decision, Luxury Cars

1. Introduction

Digital Content Marketing (DCM) has become a central component of modern marketing strategies due to the rapid growth of digital platforms and social media. DCM involves creating and distributing valuable digital content through online channels to engage target audiences and influence consumer behavior. Barbosa (2023) emphasized that the success of digital marketing strategies largely depends on effective content marketing practices, including content personalization, real-time advertising, and interactive digital experiences.

Despite the growing importance of DCM, previous studies have mainly focused on digital marketing communication and social media marketing, while limited attention has been directed toward its direct influence on consumer purchase decisions, particularly in luxury markets. Therefore, this study investigates the impact of DCM and SMIs on consumer purchase decisions in the Egyptian luxury car market.

Digital content shared online represents an important form of electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM), which consumers often perceive as more credible than traditional advertising. Social media platforms provide accessible information that supports product evaluation and purchase decisions. Mahrous (2016) highlighted that consumers increasingly rely on social media during the information search stage due to its accessibility and perceived usefulness. In this context, SMIs have become influential communication channels that shape consumer attitudes and purchase intentions through recommendations, endorsements, and interactive communication (Al-Ansi, 2023; Tao, 2020).

The Egyptian luxury car market provides a relevant context for examining the effectiveness of DCM. Luxury automotive brands rely heavily on social media platforms such as Facebook and Instagram, in addition to influencer marketing activities. However, several challenges remain, including inconsistent digital communication, limited interactive content, and insufficient product information across official digital channels. In many cases, consumers still depend on direct dealer communication or word-of-mouth to obtain detailed information before making purchase decisions.

The research problem is that although the Egyptian luxury car market experienced significant growth following the 2019 customs exemptions on European-manufactured vehicles, and consumers increasingly rely on digital platforms during purchase decisions, limited research has examined the impact of Digital Content Marketing (DCM) on purchase decisions within the luxury automotive sector in emerging markets such as Egypt. Existing studies mainly focus on isolated aspects of DCM and social media influencers without fully explaining how integrated digital content strategies influence consumer behavior. In practice, inconsistent digital content, fragmented online brand presence, and limited personalized communication continue to reduce the effectiveness of digital marketing activities in the Egyptian luxury car market. Accordingly, this study investigates the impact of DCM on consumer purchase decisions, particularly regarding online search evaluation and intention–decision to purchase.

In light of the above, the research objectives are to develop a comprehensive Digital Content Marketing (DCM) framework suitable for the Egyptian luxury automotive sector that enhances digital reach, improves customer access to information, and reduces lost sales resulting from limited or fragmented digital content. In addition, the study aims to provide practical implications and recommendations for luxury car dealers in Egypt to improve the effectiveness of their DCM strategies and enhance sales performance

2. Literature Review

2.1 Digital Content Marketing (DCM)

DCM has become one of the most important strategic tools organizations use to attract, engage, and retain customers through digital platforms and online communication channels. The rapid growth of internet usage, social media, and mobile technologies has increased organizations' dependence on digital content to influence consumer behavior and support business performance. According to Statista (2024), the global content marketing industry generated approximately USD 63 billion in revenue in 2022 and is expected to exceed USD 107 billion by 2026, highlighting the growing strategic importance of DCM across industries.

Previous studies emphasized that content marketing is an essential component of integrated marketing communication and relationship marketing strategies (Cronin, 2016). Liu and Huang (2015) argued that content marketing enables firms to attract consumers through valuable and engaging digital communication. Unlike traditional advertising, which mainly focuses on direct promotion, DCM aims to build long-term relationships by providing relevant, informative, and interactive content experiences (Bu et al., 2021).

Researchers also highlighted that consumers increasingly rely on digital content to evaluate products and reduce uncertainty before making purchase decisions. Holliman and Rowley (2014) explained that DCM includes text, graphics, videos, images, and storytelling techniques that communicate brand value and strengthen customer engagement. Similarly, Halvorson and Rach (2012) noted that consumers use digital

platforms to learn, explore, and interact with brands, making digital content an important awareness and relationship-building tool.

The importance of DCM is particularly evident in emerging markets such as Egypt, where internet penetration and smartphone usage continue to grow rapidly. Consumers increasingly depend on digital platforms such as YouTube, Instagram, and Facebook to search for information, compare products, and evaluate alternatives before making purchase decisions.

Previous studies also highlighted the role of branded digital content in influencing purchase decisions. Google (2019) reported that many consumers watch product-related videos before purchasing products. Lou and Yuan (2019) further argued that consumers follow branded digital content to obtain product information and brand-related experiences. Consequently, firms increasingly invest in educational, entertaining, and interactive digital content to improve customer engagement and loyalty.

Dimensions of Digital Content Marketing

The literature identifies several dimensions of DCM that influence consumer perceptions and purchase behavior, particularly within luxury markets. These dimensions include informative value, experiential value, unique value, social value, and functional value.

A. Informative Value: Informative value refers to the ability of digital content to provide consumers with useful, accurate, and relevant information regarding products and services. Lou and Yuan (2019) identified informative value as one of the most important characteristics of branded content because consumers expect digital content to help them understand product features, benefits, and usage. Informative digital content reduces uncertainty and supports consumers during the information search and evaluation stages of the purchase decision process.

The importance of informative value is particularly evident in high-involvement products such as luxury vehicles, where consumers require detailed specifications, comparisons, and technical information before purchase. Previous studies suggested that educational videos, product demonstrations, and explanatory digital content positively influence customer trust and purchase intentions. Informative value also enhances the credibility of SMIs, as audiences tend to trust influencers who provide useful and reliable information.

Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1a: Informative value of Digital Content Marketing has a significant positive effect on consumer purchase decisions.

B. Experiential Value: Experiential value refers to the emotional, hedonic, and entertainment aspects associated with digital brand interactions. Previous studies demonstrated that experiential value plays a significant role in influencing luxury purchase intentions and customer engagement (Vigneron & Johnson, 2004). Consumers of luxury products often seek emotional satisfaction, prestige, exclusivity, and memorable experiences in addition to functional product benefits.

Digital platforms enable firms to create immersive and engaging customer experiences through storytelling, videos, interactive content, and visually appealing communication. Jain (2019) argued that experiential value enhances consumers' entertainment and emotional involvement during digital brand interactions. Similarly, Hwang and Han (2014) found that experiential aspects positively influence brand prestige and customer perceptions within luxury markets.

Experiential value is particularly relevant in luxury automotive marketing, where brands seek to communicate exclusivity, lifestyle, innovation, and emotional attachment through digital channels. Consequently, experiential digital content strengthens customer engagement and supports purchase decisions.

Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1b: Experiential value of Digital Content Marketing has a significant positive effect on consumer purchase decisions.

C. Unique Value: Unique value reflects the exclusivity, prestige, and differentiation associated with luxury brands and their digital communication strategies. Kapferer (1998) and De Barnier et al. (2012) emphasized that uniqueness and exclusivity represent core characteristics of luxury brand consumption. Consumers often perceive luxury products as symbols of distinction and social differentiation.

Previous studies found that unique digital content positively influences brand prestige and exclusivity perceptions (Xie & Lou, 2020). Luxury consumers are attracted to exclusive information, early product reveals, premium storytelling, and distinctive digital experiences that differentiate brands from competitors. Choo et al. (2012) further explained that symbolic and self-expressive values associated with luxury brands strengthen customer-brand relationships.

Within the Egyptian luxury automotive market, unique value is particularly important due to intense competition among luxury brands, specialized automotive websites, and SMIs seeking customer attention and engagement.

Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1c: Unique value of Digital Content Marketing has a significant positive effect on consumer purchase decisions.

D. Social Value: Social value refers to the social utility consumers gain from luxury brand consumption and digital engagement. Luxury products often serve symbolic and social purposes related to status enhancement, prestige, and social recognition. Jain (2019) found that social value significantly influences luxury purchase intentions among young consumers.

DCM enhances social value by enabling consumers to associate themselves with prestigious brands, exclusive communities, and aspirational lifestyles. Choi et al. (2011) demonstrated that social value positively affects brand prestige, customer trust, and brand loyalty. Similarly, Wang et al. (2004) found that social value improves customer relationship management performance through increased customer satisfaction.

The role of social value is particularly significant within luxury automotive markets where consumers may perceive vehicle ownership as a reflection of personal identity and social status.

Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1d: Social value of Digital Content Marketing has a significant positive effect on consumer purchase decisions.

E. Functional Value: Functional value refers to the practical utility, quality, and performance benefits communicated through digital content. Consumers use digital channels to evaluate product quality, specifications, reliability, and technical performance before making purchase decisions. Lou et al. (2019) argued that consumers derive functional value from branded digital content through accessible product information and demonstrations.

Previous studies further indicated that functional value positively influences brand prestige and product evaluation (Kapferer, 1998; De Barnier et al., 2012). Xie and Lou (2020) found that functional value positively affects perceptions of luxury brand exclusivity and product quality.

Within the automotive industry, functional value is highly relevant because consumers seek detailed information regarding vehicle performance, safety, technology, and reliability. Consequently, functional digital content contributes to reducing perceived purchase risk and enhancing consumer confidence.

Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1e: Functional value of Digital Content Marketing has a significant positive effect on consumer purchase decisions.

F. Combined Effect of Informative, Experiential, and Social Value

Recent studies suggest that consumers often perceive informative, experiential, and social values collectively rather than independently within digital environments. Bui et al. (2023) argued that combining informative and experiential content creates stronger emotional engagement and positive brand experiences. Similarly, Reitsamer et al. (2026) found that multimedia digital content simultaneously delivers informational utility, emotional appeal, and social interaction.

This integrated approach is particularly important in luxury marketing, where consumers seek both rational and emotional benefits during digital interactions. Accordingly, combining informative, experiential, and social values may create a stronger influence on customer engagement and purchase decisions than each dimension individually.

Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1f: The combined effect of informative, experiential, and social values of DCM has a significant positive effect on consumer purchase decisions.

Digital Content Marketing and Consumer Behavior

Consumer behavior has changed significantly within digital environments due to the widespread use of online platforms, smartphones, and social media networks. Consumers increasingly rely on digital channels during information search, product evaluation, comparison, and post-purchase stages. High-involvement products such as vehicles require extensive information search and external evaluation before purchase decisions.

Previous studies indicated that consumers use digital content to reduce uncertainty, save time, compare alternatives, and improve purchase confidence (Pralhad & Ramaswamy, 2004). Hassan and Pektas (2020) defined purchase intention as consumers' willingness to buy a product or service in the future, which can be influenced by digital interactions and online experiences.

Within the automotive sector, Dahiya (2017) emphasized the importance of search engine optimization (SEO), branded websites, online reviews, and comparison platforms in supporting consumer purchase decisions. Consumers increasingly depend on videos, blogs, online reviews, and social media discussions to evaluate vehicle models and compare features before visiting showrooms.

Researchers further highlighted that effective DCM should be informative, interactive, visually appealing, and compatible across multiple digital devices and platforms. Digital tools such as augmented reality, 360-degree product views, virtual demonstrations, and interactive applications enhance consumer engagement and facilitate product evaluation.

Moreover, digital platforms enable consumers to share post-purchase experiences and recommendations, creating electronic eWOM that may positively or negatively influence other buyers. Consequently, firms increasingly depend on digital reputation management and customer engagement strategies to strengthen consumer trust and support purchase decisions.

Digital Content Marketing Use in Social Media

Social media platforms have significantly expanded the influence of DCM by enabling direct interaction between brands and consumers. Researchers emphasized that social media supports customer engagement through two-way communication, content sharing, and online interactions (Dolan et al., 2019; Shahbaznezhad et al., 2021).

Previous studies found that entertainment-oriented and emotionally appealing content positively influences customer engagement on social media platforms. Tafesse (2015) demonstrated that artistic and entertaining content generates higher engagement levels than purely promotional content within the automotive industry. Similarly, Swani et al. (2013) argued that emotional content in B2C markets generates stronger customer reactions and engagement than traditional informational advertising.

Social media platforms also enable firms to strengthen customer relationships through comments, likes, shares, and online discussions. Positive engagement contributes to customer loyalty, brand awareness, and purchase intentions. Consequently, DCM has become an essential tool for increasing consumer interaction and enhancing digital brand experiences.

Digital Content Marketing and Social Media Influencers

The growing popularity of SMIs has increased the importance of influencer-generated digital content in shaping consumer attitudes and purchase behavior. Previous studies demonstrated that consumers increasingly rely on influencer endorsements, reviews, and visual content when evaluating products and services (Lee et al., 2021).

Lou and Yuan (2019) argued that SMIs enhance customer trust and engagement through authentic, relatable, and interactive content. Similarly, Cheung et al. (2022) found that influencer content based on shared values and personal experiences strengthens parasocial relationships and reduces consumers' perceived risk.

Several studies further emphasized that successful influencer marketing depends on informative, experiential, and visually engaging digital content. Influencers often use storytelling, visual demonstrations, emotional communication, and product experiences to strengthen audience engagement and influence purchase decisions.

Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Digital Content Marketing has a significant positive effect on Social Media Influencers.

Designing Successful Digital Content Marketing Strategies

The effectiveness of DCM depends largely on content quality, personalization, relevance, and strategic alignment with customer needs. Previous studies suggested that successful DCM strategies should focus on customer engagement, storytelling, personalization, and value creation (Holliman & Rowley, 2014).

Researchers emphasized the importance of content personalization, innovative communication, and real-time digital interactions in improving customer experiences and marketing performance (Aker et al., 2022). Furthermore, firms increasingly use data analytics, cookies, artificial intelligence, and customer behavior analysis to develop personalized digital experiences.

Effective DCM strategies also require clear objectives related to sales growth, brand awareness, customer engagement, and customer relationship development. SEO strategies, social media communication, visual storytelling, podcasts, and influencer collaborations have become essential components of modern digital marketing strategies.

However, previous studies highlighted several challenges associated with DCM, including privacy concerns, ethical data usage, and maintaining consistency across digital channels. Consequently, firms must balance personalization and customer privacy while ensuring high-quality and trustworthy digital communication.

Social Word-of-Mouth and Digital Storytelling

Social word-of-mouth (SWOM) represents one of the most influential forms of electronic communication within digital environments. Consumers increasingly depend on online reviews, recommendations, and social media discussions to evaluate products and reduce purchase risk. Wood (2017) argued that SWOM significantly influences both pre-purchase and post-purchase consumer behavior.

Researchers further highlighted the role of digital storytelling (DST) in enhancing customer engagement and strengthening brand image. DST combines storytelling techniques with digital media tools to communicate brand values, product benefits, and emotional experiences (Tak & Panwar, 2017). Effective storytelling strategies positively influence consumer perceptions, attitudes, and purchase intentions.

Within luxury markets, storytelling allows brands to communicate exclusivity, prestige, authenticity, and lifestyle associations that strengthen emotional connections with consumers.

Digital Content Marketing Performance

Previous studies confirmed the relationship between DCM performance and organizational outcomes such as brand performance, customer relationship performance, and sales growth (Vieira et al., 2019; Hollebeek et al., 2019). Effective DCM strategies improve customer engagement, increase brand awareness, and strengthen customer loyalty.

Researchers emphasized that successful DCM performance depends on content quality, coordination across digital platforms, customer insights, and continuous content development. Firms increasingly integrate DCM with paid digital advertising, social media advertising, and SEO strategies to maximize visibility and customer reach.

Moreover, organizations frequently cooperate with external agencies and digital specialists to improve content production, visualization, and digital communication efficiency. However, firms should maintain strategic control over core brand communication activities to preserve brand consistency and customer trust.

Based on the reviewed literature, DCM represents a strategic marketing tool that significantly influences consumer behavior and purchase decisions through informative, experiential, unique, social, and functional values. Effective DCM strategies enhance customer engagement, reduce uncertainty, improve brand perceptions, and strengthen customer-brand relationships.

The literature further indicates that successful digital content should be informative, engaging, accessible, authentic, visually appealing, and aligned with customer needs. Within the luxury automotive sector, DCM plays a particularly important role due to the high involvement nature of vehicle purchase decisions and consumers' increasing reliance on digital platforms for product evaluation.

Accordingly, this study proposes the following main hypothesis:

H1: Digital Content Marketing positively influences consumer purchase decisions.

2.2 Social Media Influencer (SMI)

SMIs have become a major component of digital marketing strategies because of their ability to influence consumer attitudes, engagement, and purchase behavior through social media platforms. Brands increasingly collaborate with influencers who possess large follower bases and high engagement rates to promote products and services through reviews, recommendations, and personal experiences. According to De Veirman et al. (2017), influencer marketing allows firms to measure interaction indicators such as likes, comments, shares, and saves to evaluate influencer effectiveness and return on investment (ROI). Similarly, Bagchi (2013) emphasized that SMIs contribute significantly to digital selling through engagement, trust, and communication quality.

The effectiveness of SMIs largely depends on the emotional connection they establish with followers. Ki et al. (2020) and Tser-Yieth et al. (2025) argued that influencers create perceived emotional closeness with audiences, which positively affects purchase intention. Likewise, Ladhari et al. (2020) found that emotional attachment enhances consumer behavioral responses toward endorsed products. However, Kim et al. (2022) suggested that purchase decisions are influenced by both emotional and rational factors, especially among knowledgeable consumers.

Influencer marketing represents a communication strategy in which brands use influencers to deliver marketing messages through social media platforms. Compared to traditional celebrity endorsement, SMIs are often perceived as more credible, trustworthy, and relatable because of their direct interaction with followers (Patel, 2016; Talaverna, 2015). Freberg et al. (2011) and Ki and Kim (2019) defined SMIs as “autonomous third-party endorsers” who build social networks by sharing experiences and opinions through digital content.

The influencer marketing industry has experienced rapid global growth, with its market value expected to exceed USD 28 billion by 2026 (Garg and Bakshi, 2024). Moreover, Kim and Kim (2021) reported that 92% of consumers trust influencer recommendations, highlighting the increasing importance of influencer credibility in digital marketing environments

Traditional Influencers and Micro-Influencers

The use of celebrities and opinion leaders as marketing endorsers has long been common in consumer markets (Knoll and Matthes, 2017). Traditional celebrities possess large follower bases and strong media exposure, making them effective communication channels for brands. However, celebrity endorsement often requires substantial financial investment.

As a result, marketers increasingly rely on micro-influencers, who possess smaller but highly engaged follower communities. Unlike celebrities, micro-influencers are often perceived as more authentic, relatable, and trustworthy (Main, 2017). Their personalized communication and storytelling enhance engagement effectiveness and strengthen followers’ trust.

Technological developments have also transformed influencer marketing practices. Duani et al. (2018) observed that audiences increasingly prefer live-streamed content because of its authenticity and interactivity. Additionally, virtual influencers powered by artificial intelligence are emerging as a new form of digital endorsement. Nolan (2018) suggested that virtual influencers reduce many reputational risks associated with human celebrities and are expected to play a growing role in future digital marketing strategies.

Overall, influencer marketing has shifted from reliance on traditional celebrities toward micro-influencers and virtual influencers due to their stronger engagement, authenticity, and cost efficiency.

Dimensions of Social Media Influencer (SMI)

A. Authenticity: Authenticity is one of the most significant characteristics affecting influencer effectiveness. (Jun and Yi, 2020) distinguished between influencers motivated intrinsically and those driven mainly by commercial incentives, suggesting that intrinsically motivated influencers are perceived as more authentic. Previous studies confirmed that authenticity strengthens parasocial relationships (PSR) between influencers and followers (Cohen and Tyler, 2016; Marwick and Boyd, 2011). Moreover, (Liu and Zheng, 2024) identified authenticity as a major driver of influencer credibility, trust, and marketing effectiveness.

Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H2a: Authenticity of Social Media Influencer has a significant positive effect on consumers’ Purchase Decision.

B. Homophily: Homophily refers to the perceived similarity between influencers and followers regarding values, lifestyles, and attitudes. Consumers are more likely to trust influencers who resemble them, which reduces perceived risk and increases purchase intention. (Onofrei et al., 2022) found that homophily positively affects consumer engagement and purchase intention, while (Liu and Zheng, 2024) demonstrated that it strengthens parasocial relationships and influencer effectiveness.

Accordingly, it is hypothesized that:

H2b: Homophily of SMI has a significant positive effect on consumers' Purchase Decision.

C. Parasocial Relationship (PSR): Parasocial relationships describe the psychological connection through which consumers perceive influencers as trusted companions. (Conde and Cassias, 2023) explained that strong PSRs emerge when followers perceive similarity and emotional closeness with influencers. Several studies emphasized the role of PSRs in strengthening trust and brand credibility (Chung and Cho, 2017; Reinikainen et al., 2020).

(Lou and Kim, 2019) confirmed that PSRs positively influence followers' attitudes and purchase intentions, while (Hwang and Zhang, 2018) found that strong PSRs reduce the negative effects of persuasion knowledge on purchase intention and eWOM.

Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H2c: Parasocial relationship of Social Media Influencer has a significant positive effect on consumers' Purchase Decision.

D. Persuasion Knowledge: Persuasion knowledge refers to consumers' awareness that influencers receive compensation for product endorsements. According to (Dhanesh and Duthler, 2019), followers recognize persuasive intentions behind sponsored content and evaluate influencer credibility accordingly. Previous studies produced mixed findings regarding its impact. Some studies suggested that persuasion knowledge negatively affects trust and purchase intention (Boerman et al., 2013), while others argued that strong influencer-follower relationships reduce such negative effects (Lou, 2021; Liu and Zheng, 2024).

Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H2d: Persuasion knowledge of Social Media Influencer has a significant positive effect on consumers' Purchase Decision.

E. Purchase Intention: Purchase intention represents one of the most important indicators used to predict actual purchasing behavior. Previous studies confirmed that celebrity and influencer endorsements positively affect purchase intention through social media platforms (Kumar et al., 2023; Taillon et al., 2020). Moreover, (Liu and Zheng, 2024) identified authenticity, homophily, trust, and parasocial relationships as major factors supporting purchase intention positively.

Accordingly, it is hypothesized that:

H2e: Purchase intention of Social Media Influencer has a significant positive effect on consumers' Purchase Decision.

F. The Construct (Homophily, Parasocial Relationship, and Purchase Intention) of SMI

Factor analysis findings revealed that homophily, parasocial relationship, and purchase intention converge into a single empirical construct representing the strongest dimension within the SMI framework. These dimensions are highly interconnected, where perceived similarity strengthens parasocial relationships and ultimately enhances purchase intention (Naufal and Dewi, 2025; Jannat and Ahmed, 2025).

Consumers are more likely to trust influencers who share similar lifestyles and values, which strengthens emotional relationships and increases behavioral intention toward endorsed products. Influencers also leverage these relationships to create urgency and fear of missing out (FOMO), encouraging purchase decisions.

Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H2f: Combined effect of homophily, parasocial relationship, and purchase intention of Social Media Influencer has a significant positive effect on consumers' Purchase Decision.

Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM) and Opinion Leader Impact on Purchase Intention

(Lou and Yuan, 2019; Saima and Khan, 2020) agreed that SMI marketing relies heavily on electronic word of mouth (eWOM) and opinion leaders, who are considered a type of SMI. eWOM can positively or negatively influence users' purchase intention through reviews, recommendations, and shared experiences on social media platforms. Followers often share influencer content publicly or privately with others, increasing the spread and impact of product-related information. Opinion leaders are individuals with expertise, knowledge, or experience in a specific field who can shape followers' attitudes and behaviors. (Tobon and García-Madariaga, 2021) found that opinion leaders significantly influence followers' purchase intentions toward the products and services they endorse.

Characteristics of Social Media Influencers in the B2B Context

In B2B markets, marketers evaluate several factors when selecting influencers for marketing campaigns. (De Veirman et al., 2017) highlighted the importance of the number of followers, while (Kwak et al., 2010) emphasized retweets and mentions as indicators of influencer impact. Other important characteristics include expertise, trustworthiness, and attractiveness (Balabanis and Chatzopoulou, 2019). Additionally, customer trust in influencers and perceptions of influencer personality play a major role in influencer effectiveness (Lou and Yuan, 2019; Schouten et al., 2019).

Unlike B2C influencers, who often create content for self-enhancement and entertainment purposes, influencers in B2B contexts mainly support procurement managers and organizations by reducing uncertainty and providing reliable information regarding vendors and offerings. Since B2B purchase decisions involve lengthy evaluation and selection processes, firms increasingly use influencers through social media broadcasts to support vendor credibility and influence organizational buying decisions.

Traits that Affect Influencer Credibility

Reliability

Reliability is considered a fundamental factor influencing consumers' purchase decisions in the digital environment. (Kumar et al., 2023) defined reliability as the probability of meeting predetermined service standards, which directly influences customer preferences and purchasing behavior. Influencer credibility depends heavily on reliability, integrity, and consistency in content delivery. (Al-Dmour et al., 2019) argued that information technology and online security have increased the importance of reliability in modern business environments. Similarly, (Muñoz-Leiva et al., 2021) emphasized that influencer integrity and reliability are essential for maintaining positive consumer perceptions and long-term influence. Consumers' online browsing experience also shapes how they interact with products, brands, and influencer-generated content.

Attractiveness

Physical attractiveness is an important source of influencer credibility and positive consumer perception (Santos and Schlesinger, 2021). (Patzer, 1983) defined attractiveness as the degree to which facial traits are

pleasing to observe. Attractive individuals tend to receive more positive judgments and stronger first impressions in social and professional interactions (Villi and Koc, 2017).

Previous studies suggested that influencer attractiveness positively affects followers' perceptions and engagement. However, some studies argued that the compatibility between the influencer and the brand may be more important than physical attractiveness alone (Fleck-Dousteyssier et al., 2012). Additionally, product reliability and service quality remain important drivers of trust and purchase intention in e-commerce environments (Zuo and Gou, 2023; Saoula et al., 2023). (Wang et al., 2023) further noted that influencer reliability depends on both personal characteristics and the structure of their social networks.

Expertise

Influencers are often perceived as experts who can create emotional connections with followers and provide meaningful experiences (Santos and Schlesinger, 2021). Brands increasingly collaborate with influencers to co-create engaging customer experiences that support competitive differentiation (Castañeda García et al., 2018). Moreover, consumers seek authentic and personalized experiences, making influencer expertise an important factor in enhancing customer loyalty and engagement (Serra-Cantallos et al., 2018).

The growing use of multiple digital platforms has created challenges for brands and influencers in maintaining safe, entertaining, and satisfying shopping experiences (Marikyan et al., 2023; Orús et al., 2019). Positive online experiences contribute to customer satisfaction and long-term relationships. Furthermore, shared values between influencers and followers strengthen trust and reduce interpersonal barriers (Coulter and Coulter, 2002). (Islam et al., 2018) emphasized that value congruence between influencers and followers enhances customer attraction and positively influences purchase decisions. Consequently, influencer expertise, authenticity, attractiveness, and shared values collectively strengthen influencer credibility and marketing effectiveness.

Impact of Trust Between SMI and Followers on Purchase Decision

Trust is a critical factor in consumers' decision-making processes. When followers perceive influencers as trustworthy sources of information, they become more loyal and receptive to their recommendations (Konstantopoulou et al., 2019). (Kim and Kim, 2021) found that the effectiveness of influencer messages increases when followers trust the influencer, resulting in stronger relationships and greater marketing influence.

Several factors contribute to building trust in influencer marketing, including expertise, authenticity, reliability, and transparency (Dekavalla, 2019). In online environments, consumers may experience uncertainty regarding product information; therefore, trustworthy influencers can reduce perceived risk and positively shape purchase decisions (Singh, 2021). From a marketing perspective, trust is considered a key element in establishing and maintaining long-term relationships between brands, influencers, and consumers.

It is hypothesized that: **H2: Social media influencers are positively associated with purchase decision.**

2.3 Social Media Marketing

Consumers use social media to obtain functional information related to products, services, and purchasing decisions. Social media platforms provide convenient communication channels that help users access relevant information, reduce perceived risk, and seek advice from others. According to (Lieb, 2012), social media offers consumers educational and informative digital content that supports purchase decision-making. Through DCM, firms can provide consumers with accessible and high-quality information that enhances their understanding of products and services.

Social Media Entertainment Information and the Creation of DCM

Consumers also use social media for entertainment, relaxation, and escapism. Entertaining content generates enjoyment and satisfaction, which encourages users to engage with brands and digital content. Consequently, digital marketers aim to create interesting, playful, and emotionally appealing content to strengthen consumer engagement and brand perception. Entertaining communication positively influences brand image and enhances consumers' receptiveness toward marketing messages.

Impact of Social Media on Self-Concept

Social media enables users to express their self-concept through interactions with brands and products that reflect their personalities, lifestyles, and values. Consumers often share photos, videos, and experiences with brands to present a desired identity to others. The literature suggests that when brands align with consumers' values and self-image, they positively influence brand identity and consumer engagement. As a result, marketers pay significant attention to consumers' self-concept when designing social media marketing activities and selecting appropriate communication strategies.

Social Media Marketing Features

Hanaysha (2022) identified four key social media marketing features that directly influence purchase decisions through brand trust: interactivity, entertainment, perceived relevance, and informativeness.

A. Interactivity: Interactivity refers to the exchange of information between brands and consumers, as well as among consumers themselves. Social media platforms allow firms to communicate directly with customers and encourage information sharing about products and services. Muntinga (2011) emphasized that social media facilitates consumer interaction and supports purchasing behavior. Previous studies (Zafar, 2021; De Vries, 2012; Yeon, 2019) confirmed that interactive social media platforms positively influence consumer purchase decisions and buying behavior.

B. Entertainment: Entertainment is a key element in creating engaging and enjoyable social media content. Sharma et al. (2022) highlighted that entertaining content should be interesting and enjoyable, while Cheung et al. (2021) argued that marketers use entertaining content to create positive customer experiences and improve consumer attitudes toward brands. Studies by Buzeta et al. (2020) and Jayasingh (2019) further found that contests, games, and video-sharing activities enhance customer engagement, brand trust, and purchase intention.

C. Perceived Relevance: Perceived relevance refers to the extent to which consumers believe that marketing messages relate to their personal interests and values (Zhu & Chang, 2016). Social media enables marketers to design personalized content for specific audiences. Research indicates that customized messages and instant responses to customer inquiries strengthen brand trust and increase purchase intention (Gautam, 2017).

D. Informativeness: Informativeness refers to the ability of social media content to provide useful information about products and services. Lee and Hong (2016) stated that informative content helps marketers influence consumer behavior and attract new customers. Social media platforms also provide access to product reviews, customer experiences, and expert opinions that support informed purchase decisions. Furthermore, the widespread use of smartphones and mobile devices has increased the effectiveness of informative digital marketing activities (Chhonker et al., 2018)

Social Media Marketing Strategies (SMMS)

(Li et al., 2020) defined social media marketing strategies as organizations' integrated activities that use social media interactions to achieve marketing objectives. (Kim & Ko, 2012) identified several advantages of social media marketing, including interaction, entertainment, customization, trendiness, and electronic word of mouth. Social media enables customers to access updated information, share reviews, and interact directly with brands and other users in real time.

Furthermore, (Seo & Park, 2018) found that social media marketing activities positively influence brand image and brand awareness, which subsequently enhance electronic word of mouth and customer commitment. The literature also suggests several practical guidelines for marketers, including creating entertaining and interactive content, using stories and hashtags effectively, publishing timely and relevant posts, and providing clear and accessible product information. These strategies help strengthen customer relationships, improve engagement, and support purchase decisions.

Social Media Impact on the Marketplace

(Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010) defined social media as platforms that enable users to build networks and share information. According to (Peters et al., 2013), social media is dynamic, interactive, interconnected, and egalitarian in nature. Social media has transformed the marketplace in three major ways. First, it strengthened the connection between firms and customers through platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, X, and YouTube, where users interact based on shared interests and values. Second, it changed the nature of communication and influence through electronic word of mouth (eWOM), including reviews, recommendations, shares, likes, and comments. Third, social media generated large amounts of data that support firms in improving customer relationships and decision-making. This data is commonly described through the “3Vs”: variety, volume, and velocity. (Schweidel & Moe, 2014) noted that modern technologies facilitate the extraction and analysis of social media data, while (Gnizy, 2018) emphasized its importance for customer analysis, market research, and integrated marketing communication strategies.

Role of Social Media Marketing in B2B

The literature (Lacka & Chong, 2016; Siamagka et al., 2015) suggests that social media marketing in B2B markets depends on factors such as ease of use, perceived usefulness, commitment, innovativeness, and organizational competence. Social media marketing positively influences B2B firms through improved sales performance, customer relationships, competitive intelligence, and selling behavior (Itani et al., 2017). Furthermore, social media enhances customer loyalty by increasing trust in salespersons' integrity, benevolence, and expertise, which positively affects customer satisfaction and overall business performance.

Impact of Social Media on Consumer Interaction and Behavior

Social media has become a powerful driver of consumer behavior and purchase decisions. Platforms such as Instagram, Pinterest, and TikTok facilitate product exploration through visually appealing content shared by brands, influencers, and users. Social media also reshaped industries such as fashion by enabling influencers and consumers to share styles, trends, and preferences through interactive features including likes, shares, comments, and views. In addition, integrated shopping features on social media platforms allow consumers to purchase products directly from posts and advertisements. User-generated content and online reviews further strengthen trust and positively influence purchase decisions.

Impact of Social Media on Purchase Intention and Customer Journey

Social media plays a significant role throughout the customer journey, including pre-purchase, purchase, and post-purchase stages. (Ahmad et al., 2022) found that customers' active participation on social media enhances brand equity and purchase intention. Purchase intention refers to consumers' willingness to buy a product or service (Li et al., 2022). Recent studies (Sharma et al., 2022; Youssef et al., 2023) highlighted that social media has revolutionized marketing communication strategies. Consumers increasingly rely on reviews, recommendations, and experiences shared by other users to evaluate brands and products (Al-Gasawneh et al., 2023).

During the pre-purchase stage, consumers use social media to search for product information, compare alternatives, and evaluate reviews and eWOM (Little et al., 2020). In the purchase stage, influencers create persuasive and personalized content that facilitates decision-making and strengthens emotional connections with followers (Kumar et al., 2024). Interaction through comments, messages, and sharing also enhances

engagement and supports purchase decisions (Shakuntala & Ramantoko, 2023). In the post-purchase stage, consumers share reviews and experiences that influence potential buyers and contribute to eWOM (Gupta & Maji, 2020). Studies in Asian markets (Le et al., 2022) further highlighted the importance of ratings, comments, and images in shaping consumer trust and purchasing behavior.

Integrated Customer Care on Social Media in Purchase Decision

Social media platforms are increasingly used to provide customer care, answer inquiries, and solve customer problems. Modern customer service systems are becoming more personalized and accessible through social media applications and direct messaging features. (Haenlein, 2017) introduced the concept of “invisible CRM,” where customer engagement becomes seamless and integrated into digital platforms. AI-driven chatbots and virtual assistants enable firms to provide immediate responses and personalized support in both B2B and B2C contexts. These technologies improve customer experience, enhance agility, and positively influence purchase decisions.

Impact of Social Media on the Automotive Market in India – Case Study

A study conducted in India by (Sinha, 2016) found that the automotive sector generated a high level of online conversations through digital media platforms. Consumers increasingly relied on social media and digital content when searching for information about vehicles, comparing alternatives, and booking test drives online. The study highlighted that creative digital advertising strategies significantly influence online engagement and purchasing decisions. Similarly, a study by McKinsey (Gianluca, 2012) found that digital advertising channels strongly influence the customer journey in the automotive industry. Consumers depend heavily on websites, online reviews, and social media networks during their purchasing process.

Furthermore, (Hesterberg, 2013) revealed that most new car buyers used websites and online search tools to gather information and locate dealers. Digital media enables consumers to compare products easily, participate in online discussions, and access reviews from previous buyers. However, some consumers still prefer traditional purchasing methods due to limited technological orientation, which highlights the importance of awareness and digital education initiatives.

Key Factors Influencing Purchase Decision on Social Media

Several factors influence consumers' purchase decisions on social media platforms. First, social media acts as a valuable source of information where users seek recommendations and reviews from trusted influencers and content creators. Second, electronic word of mouth (eWOM) allows consumers to access information regarding price, quality, promotions, and customer experiences. Third, security and privacy concerns remain important factors affecting online purchasing behavior. Fourth, the quality of business content and interaction significantly influences purchase decisions, as consumers value informative and interactive communication (Kijek et al., 2020). Fifth, social media features such as ratings, comments, and images facilitate product comparison and evaluation (Aboulilah et al., 2022). Finally, firms increasingly cooperate with credible and trusted SMIs to enhance brand trust and encourage purchase decisions.

Customer Experience

(Hussain et al., 2020; Jhavar, Varshney, & Kumar, 2024) agreed that consumers evaluate products beyond their core functions and features, as their perceptions are also shaped by emotional experiences, identification, and emotional resonance. According to (Hoffman & Offutt, 2015), customer experience is one of the most influential factors affecting customers' choice of suppliers and service providers. Therefore, customer experience management (CEM) aims to align firms' capabilities with customer needs across all interaction channels to create positive experiences and mutually beneficial relationships.

One of the main components of CEM is multichannel integration, where firms seek to understand customers' preferred channels in order to design integrated strategies that match customer expectations and maximize value creation. The literature distinguishes between two categories of factors influencing

customer experience. The first category includes factors under retailers' control, such as service quality, product assortment, and pricing. The second category includes factors beyond retailers' control, such as price sensitivity, convenience seeking, and shopping enjoyment.

Shopping Enjoyment

(Johnson et al., 2015) defined shopping enjoyment as the hedonic value customers gain from shopping experiences, including entertainment, pleasure, and excitement. Physical stores and showrooms often enhance shopping enjoyment by providing comfortable waiting areas, Wi-Fi services, entertainment facilities, children's areas, and refreshments. Similarly, firms pay significant attention to their digital channels by designing user-friendly websites that are easy to navigate and visually appealing.

Social media platforms also play an important role in enhancing shopping enjoyment by creating engaging and entertaining experiences for followers and customers. Many firms organize online competitions, interactive campaigns, and promotional activities through social media platforms and influencers to increase customer engagement, satisfaction, and purchase intention during the purchasing process.

Research Framework

3. Research Methodology

This section presents the research methodology adopted in the study. It begins with an overview of the Egyptian luxury car market, followed by the research design, data collection method, conceptual framework, population and sample, sampling technique, questionnaire design, pilot study, and data analysis procedures.

Research Context

The Egyptian luxury car market has witnessed significant developments since 2019 following the implementation of the European Union customs exemption on imported vehicles. This marked a turning point for the luxury segment, increasing demand for premium, exotic, and special-edition vehicles. Long waiting lists at official dealerships encouraged many consumers to import vehicles directly from European markets (Qualitative Evidence).

The increasing demand also attracted investors and led to the emergence of numerous unofficial luxury car dealers and importers in Egypt, offering customized models and higher specifications than those available through official dealerships. These businesses expanded rapidly and established partnerships with European dealers to ensure market sustainability (Ritz Auto Salon; Voss Exotics; British Automotive; Autoboutique.eg; Elziny Auto; Edition One Auto; Autobahn; Nine One One; ESTOCIA; 9G Auto; One Way Auto; Wheels Automotive; Elite Automotive; Viking EG, n.d.).

In parallel, several international luxury brands strengthened their presence in Egypt. For example, Aston Martin officially entered the Egyptian market, while Ferrari changed its local dealership to improve sales and customer service. Additionally, Egyptian brokers based in Europe increasingly relied on social media platforms to market vehicle importation and customization services directly to Egyptian consumers.

Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative research approach to achieve the research objectives. Quantitative research is suitable for measuring variables and testing hypotheses using structured questionnaires without manipulating the study environment.

The study follows a descriptive cross-sectional design, which enables the researcher to examine consumer perceptions, attitudes, and behaviors at a specific point in time. Descriptive research is widely used to identify patterns, trends, and relationships among variables while providing reliable statistical analysis.

Research Data

The study relies on primary data collected through a survey-based questionnaire. Questionnaires are considered an effective method for collecting large amounts of consumer data in a structured and measurable form. According to Naresh Malhotra, surveys are among the most appropriate tools for measuring consumers' perceptions, attitudes, behaviors, and demographic characteristics.

Research Population and Sample

The study examines the impact of DCM and SMIs on consumers' purchase decisions in the Egyptian luxury car market. A cross-sectional approach is adopted, where data are collected once during a specific period using questionnaires (Malhotra, 2010).

The target population consists of luxury vehicle owners in Cairo and Giza, where the majority of the Egyptian luxury car market is concentrated. Determining the exact population size is difficult because luxury vehicles are purchased through multiple channels, including official dealerships, unofficial showrooms, private importers, and direct imports by customers. In addition, some vehicles remain unregistered for investment purposes, making official records less accurate indicators of the actual market size.

The study adopts a non-probability judgmental quota sampling technique due to the absence of an accurate sampling frame. This method allows the researcher to select respondents who are considered representative of the target population based on professional judgment. Judgmental quota sampling also provides flexibility in accessing luxury car owners who match the study criteria and helps generate reliable estimates of population characteristics.

The unit of analysis in this study consists of luxury car owners in Cairo and Giza, including key customers, car collectors, and automotive stakeholders. The sample size will be determined based on statistical considerations, population concentration, and accessibility of respondents within the targeted geographic areas.

Research Variable Measures

This section presents the study variables and the measurement scales adopted to test the research hypotheses. Table 1 summarizes the main variables, dimensions, measurement items, and sources adopted from previous studies.

Table 1: Measurements for Testing Hypotheses

Variable	Dimension	Sample Items	Source
Independent Variable: Digital Content Marketing (DCM)	Informative Value	This video provides relevant, timely, and useful brand information.	Ducoffe (1996); Lou et al. (2019)
	Experiential Value	Watching the videos improves my mood and provides sensory appeal.	Jain (2019)
	Unique Value	Exclusive – Valuable – Uncommon.	Vigneron & Johnson (2004)
	Social Value	Helps me stay connected with trends and others.	Cheng (2009); Dholakia et al. (2004); Oyedele & Simpson (2018)
	Functional Value	Reliable, satisfactory, and useful medium.	Cheng (2009)
Independent & Mediating Variable: Social Media Influencer (SMI)	Authenticity	The influencer behaves consistently with his/her values and appears honest.	Ilicic & Webster (2016)
	Homophily	The influencer shares similar values, preferences, and experiences with me.	Onofrei et al. (2022)
	Parasocial Relationship	I feel comfortable with and emotionally connected to the influencer.	Kim et al. (2015)
	Persuasion Knowledge	The influencer's advertisements attempt to persuade consumers to buy products.	Hwang & Zhang (2018)
	Purchase Intention	I intend to purchase products promoted by the influencer.	Yoo & Donthu (2014)
Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision	Online Search Effort	Assessment of effort required to search for product information online.	Gupta & Su (2004)
	Online Evaluation Effort	Online information is adequate for product evaluation.	Gupta & Su (2004)
	Intention to Purchase	Branded social media pages influence my intention to purchase.	Shim (2012); Huang & Chen (2006)
	Decision to Purchase	Branded social media pages affect my final purchase decision.	Shim (2012); Huang & Chen (2006)

Table 2 presents the scales used for measuring each construct

Table 2 Scales for Testing Hypotheses

Scale Type	Dimension	Variable
5-Point Likert Scale	Informative Value, Experiential Value, Social Value	DCM
	Authenticity, Purchase Decision, Intention to Purchase	SMI
5-Point Evaluation Scale	Online Search Effort, Online Evaluation Effort	Purchase Decision
Semantic Differential Scale	Unique Value	DCM

Scale Type	Dimension	Variable
7-Point Likert Scale	Functional Value	DCM
	Homophily, Parasocial Relationship, Persuasion Knowledge, Purchase Intention	SMI

Questionnaire Development

The questionnaire was first developed in English and later translated into Arabic to ensure suitability for respondents. The survey items and measurement scales were adopted from previous studies. The questionnaire measures consumers' dependence on digital channels, social media platforms, and SMIs during the luxury car purchase journey.

Different scales were used to measure the study variables. Five- and seven-point Likert scales measured consumers' agreement regarding the influence of digital content and influencers on purchase decisions. Semantic differential scales measured the perceived uniqueness and exclusivity of brand digital content. In addition, five-point evaluation scales assessed consumers' perceptions regarding the ease of searching and evaluating information through digital channels.

Pilot Study

A pilot study with ten respondents was conducted to assess the clarity of the questionnaire. Based on feedback, several video-related items were rephrased for clarity (Table 3).

Table 3: Modifications in Questionnaire Wording

Original Phrase	Revised Phrase
This video provides relevant brand info.	Available video content via digital channels provides relevant brand information.
This video provides timely brand info.	Available video content via digital channels provides timely brand information.
This video provides useful brand info.	Available video content via digital channels provides useful brand information.
This video provides valuable brand info.	Available video content via digital channels provides valuable brand information.

Data Collection

The questionnaire was distributed electronically through email and WhatsApp to ensure easy access for respondents. Data collection started on 7 July 2024. A total of 35 questionnaires were distributed, of which 27 were completed, representing a response rate of 77%. The target sample size is 50 respondents. In-depth interviews were also prepared to support the qualitative phase of the study.

The study uses Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for statistical analysis and hypothesis testing. The minimum sample size was determined using the "10-times rule." Since the highest number of structural paths directed at a construct is three, the minimum recommended sample size is 30 respondents.

4. Data Analysis

Reliability Analysis

Reliability analysis was conducted to assess the internal consistency of the measurement scales used in this study. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used as the primary reliability indicator, as it is widely accepted for evaluating Likert-scale measures. According to Joseph Hair et al. (2022), alpha values above 0.70 indicate acceptable reliability, while values above 0.90 indicate excellent reliability.

Since the study used both 5-point and 7-point Likert scales, all items were standardized using z-score transformation before conducting the analysis to ensure comparability across scales. Table 4 presents the reliability results.

Table 4: Reliability Statistics for All Variables

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Informative Value	0.949	4
Experiential Value	0.786	4
Unique Value	0.924	3
Social Value	N/A	1
Functional Value	0.953	4
Authenticity	0.899	4
Homophily	0.942	4
Parasocial Relationship	0.935	5
Persuasion Knowledge	0.894	4
Purchase Intention	0.972	4
Digital Content Marketing	0.943	16
Social Media Influencer	0.958	21
Purchase Decision	0.771	4

Source: SPSS Data Analysis

The results show that most constructs achieved high to excellent reliability. Informative Value, Unique Value, Functional Value, Homophily, Parasocial Relationship, Purchase Intention, DCM, and SMI demonstrated excellent reliability with alpha values above 0.90. Experiential Value and Purchase Decision showed acceptable reliability with values above 0.70, while Authenticity and Persuasion Knowledge also reflected strong internal consistency.

The Social Value construct consisted of a single item; therefore, Cronbach's alpha could not be calculated. Overall, the findings confirm that the measurement scales are reliable and suitable for further statistical analysis.

Factor Analysis

Factor analysis was conducted to examine the underlying structure of the measurement scales and assess construct validity by identifying common variance among items (Hair et al., 2022). Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was employed due to the exploratory nature of validating the constructs within the study context.

The suitability of the data was assessed using the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity. KMO values above 0.60 and significant Bartlett's test results ($p < 0.05$) confirmed the appropriateness of the data for factor analysis. Factors with eigenvalues greater than 1.0 were retained, while factor loadings above 0.50 were considered acceptable indicators of convergent validity (Hair et al., 2022). Varimax rotation with Kaiser normalization was applied to achieve a clearer and more interpretable factor structure.

Factor Analysis for Digital Content Marketing

Exploratory factor analysis was conducted on the sixteen items measuring DCM. The KMO value was 0.905, indicating excellent sampling adequacy, while Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 = 1429.020$, $p < 0.001$), confirming the suitability of the data for factor analysis.

The analysis extracted three components with eigenvalues greater than 1.0, explaining 75.20% of the total variance. The rotated component matrix showed strong factor loadings above 0.50 with no problematic cross-loadings.

The first component combined Informative Value, Experiential Value, and Social Value items, suggesting that respondents perceive these dimensions as interconnected aspects of DCM. The second component represented Functional Value, while the third component represented Unique Value.

Overall, the findings support a stable and interpretable three-factor structure for DCM, indicating that the construct can be represented through Combined Informative–Experiential–Social Value, Functional Value and Unique Value

Factor Analysis for Social Media Influencer

Exploratory factor analysis was performed on the twenty-one items measuring the SMI construct. The KMO value reached 0.906, indicating excellent sampling adequacy, and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 = 2302.140$, $p < 0.001$), confirming the appropriateness of the data for factor analysis.

Three components with eigenvalues above 1.0 were extracted, explaining 75.83% of the total variance. The rotated factor solution demonstrated strong factor loadings exceeding 0.50 and no significant cross-loadings.

The first component combined Homophily, Parasocial Relationship, and Purchase Intention items, reflecting respondents' tendency to perceive emotional connection, similarity, and behavioral intention as closely related dimensions. The second component represented Persuasion Knowledge, while the third component represented Authenticity. The results indicate that the SMI construct is empirically represented through three dimensions Combined Homophily–Parasocial Relationship–Purchase Intention, Persuasion Knowledge and Authenticity. These findings provide strong support for the construct validity of the SMI measurement scale.

Factor Analysis for Purchase Decision

Exploratory factor analysis was conducted on the four items measuring Purchase Decision. The KMO value was 0.603, indicating acceptable sampling adequacy, while Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 = 229.275$, $p < 0.001$), supporting the suitability of the data for factor analysis.

The analysis extracted two components with eigenvalues greater than 1.0, explaining 85.31% of the total variance. The rotated component matrix showed high factor loadings with no evidence of cross-loadings.

The first component represented Immediate Purchase Decision, reflecting respondents' readiness to engage in actual purchasing behavior. The second component represented Purchase Intention and Behavioral Tendency, reflecting consumers' likelihood of considering or recommending products prior to actual purchase. Overall, the findings indicate that Purchase Decision is a multidimensional construct consisting of two related dimensions immediate Purchase Decision and Purchase Intention and Behavioral Tendency

The factor analysis results confirm satisfactory construct validity and support the use of these extracted dimensions in subsequent correlation and regression analyses.

Descriptive Statistics

This section presents the descriptive statistics of the study variables to summarize respondents' perceptions and provide an overall understanding of the data. The analysis includes minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation values for each construct. Means indicate the average level of agreement, while standard deviations reflect the variability of responses (Hair et al., 2022). Since the variables were measured using Likert scales, descriptive statistics are appropriate for identifying general response patterns before conducting inferential analysis.

Descriptive Statistics for DCM

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics for DCM

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
DCM – Informative Value	100	1.00	5.00	3.5525	1.0626
DCM – Experiential Value	100	1.00	5.00	3.2050	0.95173
DCM – Social Value	100	1.00	5.00	3.8300	1.2310
DCM – Unique Value	100	1.00	5.00	3.5500	1.0210
DCM – Functional Value	100	1.00	7.00	4.9350	1.59134
Informative–Experiential–Social	100	1.00	5.00	3.4289	0.93230

Source: SPSS Data Analysis

The findings indicate moderately positive perceptions toward all DCM dimensions. Informative Value recorded a mean of 3.55 (SD = 1.06), suggesting that respondents generally perceived the digital content as informative. Experiential Value showed a mean of 3.21 (SD = 0.95), reflecting moderate agreement regarding the enjoyable and engaging nature of digital content. Social Value achieved the highest mean among the 5-point dimensions at 3.83 (SD = 1.23), indicating that respondents viewed digital content as socially beneficial and engaging.

Unique Value reported a mean of 3.55 (SD = 1.02), suggesting that respondents moderately perceived the content as exclusive and distinctive. Functional Value, measured on a 7-point scale, recorded a mean of 4.94 (SD = 1.59), indicating positive evaluations of the practical usefulness and effectiveness of digital content.

Overall, the combined Informative–Experiential–Social dimension recorded a mean of 3.43 (SD = 0.93), reflecting moderately favorable perceptions of DCM. The moderate standard deviations across dimensions indicate some variability in respondents' opinions.

Descriptive Statistics for Social Media Influencer

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics for Social Media Influencer

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
SMI – Authenticity	100	1.00	5.00	3.0600	0.97190
SMI – Homophily	100	1.00	7.00	4.0425	1.60021
SMI – Parasocial Relationship	100	1.00	7.00	4.1320	1.63740
SMI – Persuasion Knowledge	100	1.00	7.00	4.3275	1.51328
SMI – Purchase Intention	100	1.00	7.00	3.5250	1.75864
Homophily–Parasocial–Purchase Intention	100	1.00	7.00	3.9177	1.54966

Source: SPSS Data Analysis

Authenticity recorded a mean of 3.06 (SD = 0.97) on a 5-point scale, indicating moderate perceptions of influencer authenticity. Homophily produced a mean of 4.04 (SD = 1.60), suggesting that respondents moderately perceived similarities between themselves and influencers. Parasocial Relationship also showed moderate perceptions with a mean of 4.13 (SD = 1.64), reflecting emotional connection with influencers.

Persuasion Knowledge recorded the highest mean at 4.33 (SD = 1.51), indicating that respondents were generally aware of influencers' persuasive intentions. Purchase Intention reported a mean of 3.53 (SD = 1.76), reflecting moderate willingness to purchase products promoted by influencers.

The combined Homophily–Parasocial–Purchase Intention dimension achieved a mean of 3.92 (SD = 1.55), indicating moderate engagement and behavioral influence associated with SMIs. Overall, respondents demonstrated moderate perceptions toward influencer characteristics and their impact on purchasing behavior.

Descriptive Statistics for Purchase Decision

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics for Purchase Decision

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Online Search Evaluation	100	1.00	5.00	3.3550	0.98035
Intention–Decision to Purchase	100	1.00	5.00	3.3500	1.23807
Purchase Decision	100	1.00	5.00	3.3525	0.92938

Source: SPSS Data Analysis

Online Search Evaluation recorded a mean of 3.36 (SD = 0.98), indicating that respondents moderately rely on online information and evaluation before making purchase decisions. Intention–Decision to Purchase

showed a mean of 3.35 (SD = 1.24), reflecting moderate purchase intention and readiness to buy. At the overall level, Purchase Decision achieved a mean score of 3.35 (SD = 0.93), indicating moderately positive purchase decision behavior among respondents. These findings suggest that respondents are actively engaged in online evaluation and demonstrate balanced purchase intentions, providing a suitable basis for further inferential analysis.

Normality Test

Prior to conducting inferential statistical analysis, the normality of the study variables was examined to determine the appropriate correlation technique. Normality was assessed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro–Wilk tests (Field, 2024).

The findings show that several variables significantly deviated from normality based on the Shapiro–Wilk test ($p < 0.05$), including Informative Value, Unique Value, Social Value, Functional Value, Purchase Intention, Purchase Decision, DCM, SMI, Online Search Evaluation, and Intention–Decision to Purchase. In contrast, Experiential Value, Authenticity, Persuasion Knowledge, and the combined Homophily–Parasocial–Purchase Intention construct did not show significant deviations from normality.

The Kolmogorov–Smirnov results supported these findings, indicating inconsistent normality across the study variables. Accordingly, Spearman’s rank-order correlation was selected as the most appropriate technique for examining relationships among the variables (Field, 2024).

Correlation Test Analysis

Based on the normality test results, Spearman’s rank-order correlation (ρ) was employed to examine the relationships among the study variables. Spearman’s correlation is appropriate for non-normally distributed and Likert-scale data (Field, 2024; Hair et al., 2022). Correlation strength was interpreted as strong ($\rho > 0.50$), moderate ($\rho = 0.30–0.50$), and weak ($\rho < 0.30$) (Cohen, 1988). Statistical significance was assessed at the 0.05 and 0.01 levels.

Table 8: Spearman’s Rank Correlation Test

Variables	Online Search Evaluation	Intention Decision Purchase	Purchase Decision
Informative Value	.340**	.531**	.515**
Experiential Value	.308**	.599**	.568**
Unique Value	.376**	.267**	.403**
Social Value	.352**	.595**	.590**
Functional Value	.501**	.391**	.527**
Authenticity	.297**	.647**	.536**
Homophily	.351**	.296**	.366**
Parasocial Relationship	.274**	.387**	.396**
Persuasion Knowledge	.262**	.132	.213*
Purchase Intention	.296**	.362**	.409**
Informative–Experiential–Social	.364**	.619**	.600**
Homophily–Parasocial–Purchase Intention	.326**	.375**	.426**
DCM	.491**	.564**	.646**
SMI	.351**	.424**	.461**

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Data Analysis

The findings reveal statistically significant positive relationships between DCM dimensions and Purchase Decision. Informative Value, Experiential Value, Social Value, and Functional Value demonstrated strong positive relationships with purchase decision and intention–decision purchase, indicating that informative, engaging, socially valuable, and functional digital content positively influences consumer purchasing behavior. Unique Value showed moderate correlations, suggesting that exclusivity and uniqueness mainly affect the evaluation stage of the decision-making process.

The overall DCM construct exhibited a strong positive correlation with Purchase Decision ($\rho = 0.646$, $p < 0.01$), confirming that effective DCM significantly contributes to consumers' purchasing decisions.

Regarding SMI dimensions, Authenticity showed the strongest relationship with intention–decision purchase ($\rho = 0.647$, $p < 0.01$) and a strong relationship with overall purchase decision ($\rho = 0.536$, $p < 0.01$), emphasizing the importance of influencer credibility and trustworthiness. Homophily and Parasocial Relationship demonstrated moderate positive correlations with purchase decision dimensions, indicating that perceived similarity and emotional connection with influencers positively influence consumer behavior.

Persuasion Knowledge showed weak relationships with purchase decision variables, and its relationship with intention–decision purchase was non-significant, suggesting that awareness of persuasive intent does not necessarily prevent consumers from purchasing influencer-promoted products.

Purchase Intention demonstrated moderate positive relationships with purchase decision dimensions, confirming its importance as a behavioral outcome associated with influencer marketing activities.

The composite constructs also demonstrated meaningful relationships. Informative–Experiential–Social Value showed strong positive correlations with purchase decision variables, while Homophily–Parasocial Relationship–Purchase Intention displayed moderate positive correlations, highlighting the combined influence of emotional, social, and behavioral mechanisms on purchase behavior.

Finally, the relationship between the two independent constructs, DCM and SMI, was examined using Spearman's rank correlation. The results indicate a strong and statistically significant positive relationship between DCM and SMI constructs ($\rho = 0.631$, $p < 0.01$). This finding suggests that effective DCM strategies are closely associated with stronger influencer-related perceptions and engagement.

Regression Analysis

Regression analysis was conducted to examine the predictive relationships between DCM, SMI dimensions, and purchase decision outcomes, including overall purchase decision, online search evaluation, and intention–decision to purchase. Regression analysis enables the assessment of the extent to which independent variables explain variations in the dependent variable and identify the most influential predictors (Hair et al., 2019).

The analysis was organized into three model sets. The first model examined the impact of the composite constructs of DCM and SMI on purchase decision outcomes. The second model assessed the effects of the individual DCM dimensions and the combined Informative–Experiential–Social construct. The third model evaluated the influence of SMI dimensions and the combined Homophily–Parasocial–Purchase Intention construct.

Model evaluation was based on the coefficient of determination (R^2), F-statistics, beta coefficients, and significance levels. R^2 indicates the proportion of variance explained by the independent variables, while the F-statistic assesses overall model significance. Statistical significance was evaluated at $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$ (Field, 2024).

Model Set 1: Composite Constructs → Purchase Decision Outcomes

Model Set 1 examined the impact of DCM and SMI on overall purchase decision, online search evaluation, and intention–decision to purchase.

Table 9: Regression Model Summary for Model Set 1

Model	Predictor	Beta	t	Sig.	R ²	F
1a Purchase Decision	DCM	.627	6.410	.000	.521	52.680
	SMI	.127	1.298	.198		
1b Online Search Evaluation	DCM	.489	4.170	.000	.312	21.947
	SMI	.093	.795	.428		
1c Intention–Decision Purchase	DCM	.556	5.130	.000	.413	34.165
	SMI	.117	1.085	.281		

Source: SPSS Data Analysis

The results indicate that all three models are statistically significant. DCM consistently demonstrates a strong positive and significant effect across all purchase decision outcomes. In contrast, SMI does not exhibit a statistically significant direct effect when DCM is included in the models. These findings suggest that DCM is the dominant predictor of consumer purchase behavior.

Model Set 2: DCM Dimensions → Purchase Decision Outcomes

Model Set 2 assessed the influence of individual DCM dimensions and the combined Informative–Experiential–Social construct on purchase decision outcomes.

Table 10: Regression Model Summary for Model Set 2

Model	Significant Predictors	Beta	Sig.	R ²
2a Purchase Decision	Experiential Value	.264	.020	.555
	Social Value	.296	.007	
2b Purchase Decision	Informative–Experiential–Social	.548	.000	.520
2c Online Search Evaluation	Functional Value	.293	.012	.325
2d Online Search Evaluation	Functional Value	.278	.017	.314
	Informative–Experiential–Social	.255	.020	
2e Intention–Decision Purchase	Social Value	.389	.001	.500
	Experiential Value	.235	.050	
2f Intention–Decision Purchase	Informative–Experiential–Social	.636	.000	.452

Source: SPSS Data Analysis

The findings demonstrate that Experiential Value and Social Value are the strongest DCM predictors of purchase decision outcomes. Functional Value is particularly influential during the online search and evaluation stage. Moreover, the combined Informative–Experiential–Social construct consistently shows strong predictive power, supporting the importance of integrated digital content experiences in influencing consumer decisions.

Model Set 3: SMI Dimensions → Purchase Decision Outcomes

Model Set 3 examined the impact of SMI dimensions and the combined Homophily–Parasocial–Purchase Intention construct on purchase decision outcomes.

Table 11: Regression Model Summary for Model Set 3

Model	Significant Predictors	Beta	Sig.	R ²
3a Purchase Decision	Authenticity	.562	.000	.426

Model	Significant Predictors	Beta	Sig.	R ²
3b Purchase Decision	Authenticity	.560	.000	.424
3c Online Search Evaluation	No significant predictors	—	—	.225
3d Online Search Evaluation	No significant predictors	—	—	.197
3e Intention–Decision Purchase	Authenticity	.705	.000	.469
3f Intention–Decision Purchase	Authenticity	.711	.000	.463

Source: SPSS Data Analysis

The results reveal that Authenticity is the only consistent and significant predictor across all SMI regression models. Other dimensions, including Homophily, Parasocial Relationship, Persuasion Knowledge, and Purchase Intention, do not demonstrate significant direct effects when authenticity is controlled for. Additionally, influencer-related variables show limited influence on online search evaluation.

Overall, the regression findings emphasize the dominant role of DCM in shaping purchase decisions. Within DCM dimensions, experiential and social aspects exert the strongest influence, while functional value supports online evaluation behavior. Regarding influencer marketing, authenticity emerges as the key determinant of influencer effectiveness, highlighting the importance of credible and genuine influencer communication in driving purchase intentions and decisions.

5. Discussion of the Results

This research investigated the impact of Digital Content Marketing (DCM) on purchase decision within the Egyptian luxury car market. The study examined DCM through five dimensions: informative, functional, social, experiential, and unique values. The Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) revealed that DCM is more effectively represented through three core dimensions: the combined informative–experiential–social value construct, functional value, and unique value. The findings indicate that integrated digital content dimensions exert stronger influence on consumer purchase decision than isolated dimensions, highlighting the importance of comprehensive digital content strategies.

The study also examined the role of Social Media Influencers (SMIs) in supporting consumers' purchase decisions. The SMI is best represented through two core dimensions: authenticity and the combined homophily–parasocial–purchase intention construct. In addition, purchase decision was identified as a multidimensional construct consisting of online search evaluation and intention–decision to purchase.

The findings revealed that DCM is a strong predictor of purchase decision and significantly influences consumers' behavioral outcomes. High-quality digital content enhances consumer engagement, improves evaluation processes, and strengthens purchase intention. These findings are consistent with Daniela (2016) and Gautam and Sharma (2017).

Regarding informative value, respondents perceived DCM as moderately informative; however, informative value did not exert a significant direct effect when examined independently. Its influence became stronger when integrated with experiential and social dimensions. This suggests that luxury consumers require content that combines information with emotional and social engagement rather than relying solely on informational content. The findings are consistent with Xie and Lou (2020).

The analysis further revealed that experiential value plays a significant role in enhancing emotional engagement and purchase behavior. Strong relationships were identified between experiential value, purchase decision, and intention–decision to purchase. These findings indicate that enjoyable and experience-driven digital content positively shapes luxury consumers' attitudes and behavioral intentions, supporting the findings of Jain (2019) and Xie and Lou (2020).

In contrast, unique value did not significantly predict purchase decision despite respondents moderately perceiving digital content as exclusive and distinctive. This finding indicates that exclusivity alone may not

be sufficient to influence purchase behavior unless accompanied by stronger functional, experiential, or social content elements.

The findings also demonstrated that social value positively influences purchase decision and intention–decision to purchase. Consumers perceived socially engaging and interactive digital content as valuable in enhancing social image and interaction. These results highlight the importance of social influence and shareable content in digital marketing strategies and partially align with Xie and Lou (2020).

Functional value also emerged as an important determinant of purchase decision, particularly during the online search and evaluation stage. Consumers relied heavily on functional and performance-related information while evaluating luxury vehicles online. The findings partially align with Xie and Lou (2020).

The combined informative–experiential–social value construct emerged as one of the strongest predictors of purchase decision and intention–decision to purchase. The findings demonstrate that integrated informational, emotional, and social content creates stronger consumer influence than isolated dimensions. This suggests that digital marketing strategies should focus on delivering comprehensive content experiences.

Regarding SMI, the findings revealed moderate positive associations between influencer marketing and purchase decision. However, the regression analysis demonstrated limited direct influence when DCM was included in the model. This indicates that influencer effectiveness depends largely on the quality and credibility of the associated digital content rather than influencer presence alone. These findings are consistent with Moreno-Lopez (2023), Kutz (2024), and Deepika (2023).

Among all influencer dimensions, authenticity emerged as the strongest and most consistent predictor of purchase decision outcomes. The analysis confirmed that authentic influencers enhance consumer trust, credibility, and purchase intention. This finding highlights the strategic importance of authenticity in influencer marketing and aligns with Lew and Looi (2026), Kutz (2024), and Deepika (2023).

In contrast, homophily, parasocial relationship, persuasion knowledge, and purchase intention failed to significantly predict purchase behavior despite showing moderate descriptive relationships. These findings suggest that relational closeness and follower identification alone are insufficient to directly influence luxury car purchase decisions when authenticity and content quality are considered.

Finally, the analysis revealed a strong and statistically significant positive relationship between DCM and SMI. This indicates that influencer effectiveness is strongly connected to the quality and value of digital content. The findings suggest that influencer marketing becomes more effective when supported by integrated and high-quality DCM strategies, consistent with Nadsı and Cheung (2026).

Theoretical Implications

The findings demonstrate that DCM has a significant positive impact on consumers' purchase decision, whereas SMI constructs did not exhibit statistically significant effects once DCM was included in the regression models. Although SMI showed positive associations at the correlational level, its explanatory contribution became limited when the quality of digital content was simultaneously considered. These findings support prioritizing content-driven digital strategies over influencer presence alone in shaping consumer purchase behavior.

The study further confirms that experiential and social values of digital content are more influential than purely informational or uniqueness-oriented dimensions. The regression analysis revealed that the combined informative–experiential–social value construct exerts stronger and more stable influence on purchase decision outcomes than isolated dimensions. This supports the importance of integrated informational, emotional, and social content experiences in digital marketing research.

Additionally, consumers rely on both functional clarity and integrated informational–emotional–social cues during the online search and evaluation stage. Functional value was particularly important during online information search, while social endorsement and emotional engagement emerged as key drivers of intention–decision to purchase. Informative value alone showed limited explanatory power but became influential when combined with experiential and social dimensions.

Regarding SMI dimensions, authenticity emerged as the only consistently significant predictor across purchase decision outcomes. The findings indicate that influencer credibility and sincerity represent the core mechanism through which influencer marketing affects consumer behavior. In contrast, homophily and parasocial relationship did not independently predict purchase decision when authenticity was controlled for.

The results also suggest that SMI characteristics play a limited role during the online search and evaluation stage, where consumers rely more heavily on content-related and functional information sources. Overall, the study contributes to digital marketing literature by demonstrating that integrated digital content value is more influential than influencer-related relational mechanisms in the luxury automotive context.

Managerial Implications

The study findings provide several practical implications for automotive firms and digital marketers operating in the Egyptian luxury car market.

First, automotive companies should improve the informative quality of their digital content by providing realistic visuals, detailed specifications, and comprehensive product information.

Second, Automotive brands should invest in creating distinctive and exclusive digital content across websites and social media platforms to strengthen engagement and competitive differentiation.

Third, marketers should focus on creating emotionally engaging, socially interactive, and shareable content experiences rather than relying solely on traditional informational advertising approaches.

Finally, Consumers in the luxury automotive market appear to rely more on content quality and functional information than on influencer endorsement. Consequently, firms should allocate greater marketing investment toward improving branded digital content quality and engagement channels, while using influencer marketing more selectively for brand awareness, public relations, and promotional activities.

Limitations and Future Research

This study used a non-probability judgmental quota sample drawn from owners of premium and exotic cars in Egypt. Therefore, the findings may have limited generalizability. Future studies are recommended to use larger and more diverse samples to improve external validity. In addition, the research context was limited to the luxury automotive sector within the Egyptian market. Future research may validate the findings across different product and service sectors and in other countries to enhance the applicability of the results.

Furthermore, future studies may conduct comparative research to examine differences in the impact of DCM on purchase decision across products, services, or different market contexts. The current findings also suggest the importance of further examining online search evaluation and intention–decision to purchase as independent behavioral outcomes. In particular, future research could investigate the influence of functional value and the combined informative–experiential–social value construct on online search evaluation in greater depth.

The study also identified several relationships that may offer valuable opportunities for future research. While the current study focused primarily on purchase decision, future studies should examine actual consumer behavior and post-purchase outcomes to provide deeper understanding of digital consumer decision-making. Additional research may also explore the direct and indirect effects of DCM dimensions on intention–decision to purchase across different contexts and industries.

Regarding SMI variables, the findings revealed relatively limited direct influence compared to DCM. However, some SMI dimensions demonstrated meaningful correlational relationships that may become significant in different markets or product categories. Future studies are therefore encouraged to examine the impact of SMI dimensions on online search evaluation and intention–decision to purchase in other contexts, particularly in industries where influencer marketing plays a more dominant role.

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